

THE CURRENT SECURITY SITUATION AT MAJOR EVENTS FROM AN OFFICIAL PERSPECTIVE

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Abstract

This paper examines the current security situation at major events from the perspective of public administration. It analyses the challenges posed by evolving threats, such as terrorism and cyberattacks, and explores innovative strategies for enhancing safety. Key aspects include the integration of modern security technologies, effective collaboration between public authorities and private security services, and adherence to legal frameworks. Case studies, including the Munich Oktoberfest and the 2024 European Championships, illustrate the application of these strategies in practice. The findings underscore the importance of proactive planning and continuous adaptation to ensure public safety at large-scale events.

Keywords: Public administration, Public-Private-Partnership, Major Events, Risk Analysis, Terrorism Prevention, Legal Framework

1 INTRODUCTION

This paper deals with the current security situation at major events, especially from the perspective of the authorities. Extremism has long been a threat to social peace and security. But with the ad-vent of digital technologies, the way extremism works has changed, according to (von Berg, et. al, 2023). This paper analyses the opportunities and difficulties associated with securing major events.

1.1 Problem Definition

The problem arises from the increasing change in the security situation at major events. The main reasons for this will be analysed.

1.2 Objectives and Research Question

The aim of the paper is to present the tasks of public administration in order to be able to organise major events in the current security situation. The following research question is answered in this paper: "What impact does the current security situation at major events have on public administration?"

1.3 Structure of the Work

The introduction describes the problem, the objective and research question as well as the structure of the thesis. The following chapters explain basic terms, analyse the current security situation at major events, explain security strategies and measures, outline the legal framework, present the impact on public administration, provide an outlook and recommendations, and conclude with a summary of findings.

2 FOUNDATIONS

This chapter explains the background knowledge on the current security situation at major events and its relevance in the public administration sector.

2.1 Definition of Major Events

The exact definition of a major event varies between smaller municipalities/rural areas and larger cities. Some federal states; see Table 1, speak of a major event if there are more than 1,000 participants.

Bundesland	Definition Großveranstaltungen	Aktuelle Handhabung
Baden-Württemberg	keine präzise Festlegung	> 1.000 Teilnehmer
Bayern	keine präzise Festlegung	/
Berlin	keine präzise Festlegung	> 1.000 Teilnehmer
Brandenburg	keine präzise Festlegung	/
Bremen	keine präzise Festlegung	/
Hamburg	keine präzise Festlegung	> 1.000 Teilnehmer
Hessen	keine präzise Festlegung	/
Mecklenburg-Vorpommern	keine präzise Festlegung	/
Niedersachsen	keine präzise Festlegung	> 1.000 Teilnehmer
Nordrhein-Westfalen	1) tägliche Besucherzahl von > 100.000. 2) Besucherzahl > ein Drittel der Einwohnerzahl u. mind. 5.000 Besucher zeitgleich auf Gelände. 3) verfügt über erhöhtes Gefährdungspotenzial	/
Rheinland-Pfalz	keine präzise Festlegung	/
Saarland	keine präzise Festlegung	/
Sachsen	keine präzise Festlegung	/
Sachsen-Anhalt	keine präzise Festlegung	> 1.000 Teilnehmer
Schleswig-Holstein	öffentliche o. private Veranstaltung mit > 1.000 Personen	> 1.000 Teilnehmer

Table 1: Definition of major events (Stadionwelt, 2020)

2.2 Security at Major Events

It was only at the beginning of August 2024 that the Taylor Swift concert in Vienna, for which 200,000 fans were expected for three concerts, was cancelled at short notice less than 24 hours before the start (P3 Security, 2024). The reason for this was a planned mass attack on innocent concert-goers. It became known that employees of the contracted security company were involved in the dangerous plot. Security companies and organisers had criminally neglected their duty to guarantee security. This example shows that the selection and training of security personnel at events is critical. Security personnel must be well trained, experienced and trustworthy.

2.3 Relevance in the Public Administration Sector

The current security situation at major events requires special attention and proactive measures from the public administration. Due to the growing threats of terrorism, cyber-attacks and other security-related incidents, it is crucial to develop comprehensive security concepts. These should include close cooperation

between the police, emergency services and event organisers. The public administration has a key role in planning and implementing security strategies to ensure both the safety of participants and public confidence in the event and its organisers. An inclusive security strategy helps to minimise potential risks and enables quick and effective action in the event of an emergency.

The book "Führen von Einsatzorganisationen in der Chaosphase" (Röttinger, 2024) describes how cooperation between the police, fire brigade, rescue service and Special Forces works.

Figure 1 below describes public expenditure on stadium-related police operations vs. expenditure by clubs on security services (Röttinger 2, 2024).

Figure 1: Public expenditure for stadium-related police operations vs. expenditure by clubs for security services (Röttinger 2, 2024)

3 THE CURRENT SECURITY SITUATION AT MAJOR EVENTS

This chapter takes a closer look at the current security situation at major events.

3.1 Safety Requirements and Regulations

In order to be able to identify/analyse the risks/dangers of an event, these must be identified and analysed in a risk analysis, see Figure 2.

Figure 2: Identifying dangers Event (City marketing, 2023)

Stricter access controls, the implementation of video surveillance systems and the provision of security staff for major events are required. Organisers must draw up emergency plans that enable a rapid response to security incidents (Buchmann et al., 2017).

Identified and analysed risks are assessed in the next step with regard to their potential to jeopardise the protection goals:

Figure 3: Meeting measures (Stadtmarketing, 2023)

Measures must be taken in the red area of Figure 3, measures should be taken in the yellow area and no measures are required in the green area.

3.2 The Challenge of Security Planning

The challenges include controlling and monitoring large crowds, effective emergency management, preventing dangerous situations, effective communication and dealing with unforeseen events (Kupke, 2022).

3.3 Case Studies of Current Major Events

Security is also a top priority at another major event, the Munich Oktoberfest. For example, there is a sophisticated security concept with checks at the entrances, a ban on large bags, knives and glass bottles, a high police presence, retractable bollards and concrete flower buckets to prevent car attacks (ZDF, 2024).

"There were 45 simple and 14 dangerous assaults. Twelve times resistance was offered to emergency services and seven times they were physically assaulted. Overall, the figures for violent crime were slightly down. It was a peaceful Oktoberfest. And it was a safe Oktoberfest", the Munich police also summarised. The number of offences fell by around 25 percent (ZDF 3, 2024)."

To secure the 2024 European Championships in Germany, there were border controls with Switzerland, the Czech Republic and Poland as well as access controls with metal detectors and sniffer dogs at the stadiums and people and bag checks at the fan zones. This will prevent weapons or explosives from entering the crowds (ZDF 2, 2024).

"In the period from 7 June to 15 July 2024, 1,112 arrest warrants were executed, around 8,300 unauthorised entries were registered and over 100 hooligans were prevented from entering Germany (BMI, 2024)."

4 SAFETY STRATEGIES AND MEASURES

This chapter deals with security strategies and measures in connection with major events.

4.1 Risk Analysis and Hazard Prevention

Carrying out a detailed risk analysis is a central component of security planning for major events. The aim of this analysis is to recognise and assess potential dangers at an early stage in order to derive suitable preventative measures. The type of event, the expected number of participants and the event location are of crucial importance. These factors serve as the basis for creating threat scenarios, which are then incorporated into the development of the security concept (von zur Mühlen, 2023).

4.2 Use of Security Technologies

The use of security technologies is becoming increasingly important as part of security concepts for major events. These include surveillance cameras, metal detectors, drones for aerial surveillance and digital access control systems. These technologies help to identify potentially dangerous behaviour at an early stage and initiate countermeasures immediately. In addition, the use of a security guard register, in which all security personnel are recorded, creates more transparency and control. The mandatory registration and verification of security guards ensures that only qualified personnel are deployed. As can be seen in Figure 4, the turnover of security service providers in Germany is increasing.

Figure 4: Leading security service providers in Germany (BDSW, 2023)

4.3 Cooperation between Security Authorities and Private Security Services

Cooperation between security authorities and private security services is important in the security of major events. While security authorities are responsible for overarching tasks such as hazard prevention and emergency management, private security services take care of operational tasks such as access control, identity checks and surveillance of the event site (Olfermann et al., 2022).

5 LEGAL FRAMEWORK

This chapter describes the legal framework conditions in connection with major events.

5.1 National Laws and Regulations

In Germany, the Assembly Act, the Events Act and state-specific and municipal regulations govern the regulation of major events. They define which security measures organisers must implement, e.g. in the areas of emergency planning, fire protection, escape routes and the permitted number of participants. Requirements for the involvement of private security services and co-operation with state security authorities are also clearly defined.

5.2 European Security Requirements

European security regulations set uniform standards for the protection of public safety and participants in the EU member states. Important regulations include, for example, the EU directives on combating terrorism and the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), which regulate the protection of personal data (Voigt et al., 2024). Table 2 shows that Germany is the frontrunner in terms of data protection violations.

	Land	Datenschutzverstöße seit DSGVO	Datenschutzverstöße: Veränderung im Pandemiejahr	Bußgelder
1	Deutschland	77.747	+76,2 %	69 Mio. €
2	Niederlande	66.527	-2,4 %	2,5 Mio. €
3	Vereinigtes Königreich	30.536	-27,9 %	44 Mio. €
4	Dänemark	18.938	+36,2 %	571.000 €
5	Irland	17.131	-1,5 %	715.000 €

Table 2: Top 5 countries with the most data breaches since the introduction of the GDPR (data security, 2021)

These regulations set minimum requirements for security planning, for example with regard to the deployment of security services, the protection of critical infrastructure and cooperation between national and European security authorities. The harmonisation of security standards facilitates cross-border cooperation, particularly at major international events.

5.3 Liability and Responsibilities

Liability and responsibilities affect the safety of participants and the legal consequences in the event of incidents, as event organisers are responsible for complying with the relevant laws and safety regulations. If accidents or safety incidents occur, both the organisers and the security staff, service providers or suppliers used can be held liable (Buchmann et al., 2017).

6 IMPACT ON PUBLIC ADMINISTRATION

This chapter presents the effects of the current security situation on public administration.

6.1 Administrative Tasks in Security Coordination

The first step is to obtain authorisation for the event so that all legal requirements and safety standards are met. Furthermore, a security concept must be developed and the security staff must be trained. Finally, the security measures taken are evaluated and incidents documented in order to improve the planning of future events.

6.2 Challenges for the Local Administration

One of the biggest challenges is ensuring public safety, which requires close cooperation with various security authorities and private service providers. In addition, resources must be deployed efficiently in order to fulfil the infrastructure, traffic and emergency management requirements. The interests of local residents and the minimisation of disruptions during the event must also be taken into account.

6.3 Budget and Personnel Planning

A well-planned budget not only takes into account the costs for venue hire and technical equipment, but also for security measures, licences, marketing and personnel. Personnel planning is also important, as it ensures that sufficient qualified staff are available for various tasks, such as security, admission control and guest services (Gerlach, 2023).

7 OUTLOOK AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This chapter provides an outlook on future developments in the security of major events and recommendations for public administration.

7.1 Future Developments in the Security of Major Events

The use of modern technologies, such as AI, biometric recognition and drones, enables threats to be recognised at an early stage. Digital platforms and real-time communication enable security forces to react quickly. Resources must be optimally utilised and uniform security standards established.

7.2 Recommendations for Action for Public Administration

Initially, comprehensive planning is carried out at an early stage, involving all relevant stakeholders, including security authorities, private service providers and local residents. It is also recommended that the administration uses modern technologies. Transparent communication with the public can create trust and promote acceptance of the event (Catakli, 2022).

8 CONCLUSION

The conclusion summarises the most important findings of the work, identifies open questions and provides an outlook for future developments.

This paper provides a comprehensive overview of the opportunities and difficulties associated with securing major events. By systematically analysing the various aspects, important insights are gained for further research and practice.

The digital age has opened up new opportunities for preventing extremism, but at the same time harbours a multitude of challenges. The fight against extremism in the digital space ranges from innovative technologies to the mobilisation of online communities. Through the use of artificial intelligence, data analysis and social media monitoring, extremist activities can be recognised at an early stage and countermeasures can be taken.

The current security situation at major events is characterised by challenges. Increasing threats from terrorism and other security-related risks require national and European security requirements to be taken into account.

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